

Bone Reconstruction of The Humerus Using The Mesquite Technique After Plasmocytoma Resection: A Case Report

Carolina Pereira Vieira¹, Robson Emiliano José de Freitas¹, Thatiane Francielly de Almeida²,
Esther de Oliveira Santos Gomes¹, Fernanda Grazielle da Silva Azevedo Nora^{3*}, Francisco Ramiro
Cavalcante¹

¹Department of Orthopedics and Traumatology, IOG – Instituto Ortopédico de Goiânia, Goiânia - GO, Brazil

²Department of Medicine, Ceuma University – São Luis, Maranhão, Brazil

³Faculty of Physical Education and Dance, UFG – Federal University of Goiás Avenida Esperança s/n, Campus Samambaia, Goiânia, GO, Brazil

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***Corresponding author:** Fernanda Grazielle da Silva Azevedo Nora, Faculty of Physical Education and Dance, UFG–Federal University of Goiás, Avenida Esperança s/n, Campus Samambaia, Goiânia, GO, Brazil

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ABSTRACT

The Masquelet technique has had satisfactory results in the reconstruction of bone defects caused by complex fractures, bone infections, loss of bone tissue due to tumors or other medical conditions. Therefore, the objective of the present study is to report a case of plasmacytoma in the humeral diaphysis that resulted in bone loss of 13 cm after its resection in which this technique was used in the reconstruction. This is a case report study of a female patient, 54 years old, diagnosed with a diaphyseal fracture in the left humerus, radiographic examination demonstrated that it was a pathological fracture. Therefore, radiotherapy and surgery were performed as treatment. Therefore, the Masquelet technique demonstrated good bone consolidation after tumor resection and a good functional result.

Keywords: Masquelet Technique; Induced Membrane Technique; Bone defect; Bone loss; Fracture; Humerus

INTRODUCTION

The treatment of large bone losses after tumor resection of the arm bones is a challenge for the field of orthopedics.

One treatment option for this bone loss is the Masquelet technique, it is a surgical approach used in the reconstruction of critical or segmental bone defects, it has been successfully used to treat complex fractures, bone loss due to chronic infections and tumor resection.^[1-4]

This technique involves two steps, the first of which is called the implantation space, where a temporary implant, such as a porous polyethylene mesh, is placed in the empty space created by bone loss. This implant helps maintain the space and encourages the formation of a body-induced membrane, also known as "Masquelet's membrane". The second stage is called membrane induction, where the space created by the implant is filled with autologous bone graft (from the patient himself) or bone substitute material. The porous polyethylene implant, by acting as a temporary space, induces the formation of this membrane around it. This membrane contains a network of blood vessels that supply nutrients to the bone graft^[1-4] Therefore, after this second stage, the temporary implant is removed and the space is filled with bone graft or filling material, as the membrane induces the regeneration and growth of new bone tissue, thus allowing the reconstruction of the bone defect caused, for example, by tumor resection.^[1-4]

Therefore, the masquelet technique is considered useful in situations where bone loss is significant and spontaneous regeneration is difficult. Therefore, this case report involved bone loss in the humerus, which occurred after tumor resection.

CASE REPORT

54-year-old woman, left-handed, with a history of hypertension, came to the hospital for limited Range of Motion (ROM) and traumatic pain in her left arm, which limits her movements to perform activities of daily living. With a history of pathological fracture in the left arm, the patient underwent an X-ray examination, which showed an extensive lytic lesion in the humeral diaphysis, not very expansive, with cortical insufflation (Figure 1). Subsequently, the patient underwent Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) of the left arm, revealing a solid lesion suggestive of myeloma. Therefore, a biopsy was requested for further evaluation, in which he had the diagnosis of Plasmacytoma / Multiple Myeloma.

The patient was submitted to 23 sessions of radiotherapy with doses of up to 44Gy (Figure 1). pectoralis and resection of the bone lesion in an extension of 13 cm and fixation with a locking plate of the Philo's type, shortening it by around 3 cm to minimize the gap, the bone defect was filled with cement with antibiotics (Figure 2).

After 10 weeks of recovery, the patient was again submitted to a surgical procedure, in which the cement was removed, and the bone defect was filled with homologous bone graft taken from the anterior portion of the right and left iliac bone (Figure 3).

At 2, 4 and 6 months of postoperative follow-up, the patient had a well-integrated bone graft with range of motion, as well as resolution of all previously reported symptoms with return to daily life activities.

(a) Humerus before Radiotherapy Sessions

(b) Humerus After Radiotherapy Sessions

Figure 1: X-ray of the Humerus before and after radiotherapy sessions.

Humerus after placement of cement and fixation plate – Step 1: Masquelet technique

Figure 2: Rx of the Humerus after placement of cement and fixation plate - Step 1 of the Masquelet Technique.

Humerus after bone graft placement – Step 2: Masquelet technique

Figure 3: X-ray of the Humerus after placement of the bone graft – Step 2 of the Masquelet Technique.

DISCUSSION

This article presents the treatment of a complex humerus injury using the Masquelet technique, demonstrating that large bone losses can be managed without the use of a bone transport.

Masquelet's technique involves forming a vascularized membrane and filling the defect with autologous bone graft. The technique involves the use of a cement spacer with an antibiotic, which leads to the formation of the membrane that prevents bone graft resorption and creates an ideal environment for healing.^[5-7]

Mukhopadhaya et al,^[7] presented a case of fracture of the humeral shaft after primary surgery with active signs of infection and non-consolidation of bone, therefore the Masquelet technique was used as a therapeutic resource, which helped to obtain good functional results and to control the large bone loss in infected pseudarthrosis of the humerus.

Yaokreh et al,^[8] reported the case of a 12-year-old male adolescent diagnosed with chronic osteomyelitis of the left humerus, presenting with a pathological fracture of the humerus. The two-stage Masquelet technique was used for treatment. As the first stage, a sequestrectomy removing the entire humeral diaphysis (25 cm) with conservation of the humeral blade followed by the implantation of a cement spacer in the bone defect and stabilization with 2 Kirschner wires and a thoraco-brachial mold. Eleven months after the first stage, the second stage was performed, which consisted of placing a cancellous autograft associated with a non-vascularized free fibular graft (12 cm). Bone corticalization was achieved after 11 months. After 43 weeks, the patient obtained a degree of satisfaction with the therapeutic procedure, despite still having joint stiffness.

CONCLUSION

The Masquelet technique is a relatively simple surgical technique for reconstructing segmental bone defects of any size. The use of this technique allows patients to experience discomfort in bone transport with prolonged use of an external fixator. Therefore, the presented case demonstrated that the use of the induced membrane technique allows achieving satisfactory functional results in patients with severe bone defects after tumor resection in the humerus.

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